

MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC ASSESSMENT OF LYMPH NODES IN RATS WITH CHRONIC CARBON DIOXIDE POISONING AFTER TREATMENT

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Abstract. For several centuries, the safflor plant has been used in folk medicine to treat cardiovascular diseases, edema of various etiologies, improve blood circulation and helps with various types of pain. In addition, it has been used as an effective remedy for menstrual disorders, various hematomas and hemorrhages, injuries, as well as in postoperative rehabilitation. On morphological images, we saw the result of eliminating various types of dilation by reducing stagnation of lymph fluid in all anatomical structures of the lymph node by reducing the expansion of lymph vessels.

Keywords: Safflor, varicose veins, macrophage, histocyte, subcapsular, reticulocyte, germinal, lymphocyte, morphology, immunity, reactive changes, lymph node, lymphoid follicle.

Relevance.

The oil of the Safflor plant is rich in vitamins E and K and has strong natural antioxidant properties. The oil of the Safflor plant contains many important acids and elements necessary for the body, and its ability to be quickly absorbed into the body and penetrate into the deep layers of the epidermis is very convenient. It is recommended for people with skin diseases because of the vitamin K content and as a stimulant to restore the function of blood vessels. The oil of the Safflor plant can affect the structure and density of capillaries[1,2,3].

Materials and methods. The experiments were conducted on 100 white female mongrel rats born in a vivarium.

In our study, rats chronically poisoned by carbon monoxide were treated with intragastric tincture of the safflor plant in a volume of 1 ml for 14 days through a gastric metal tube.

The aim of the study is to determine the morphological and morphometric changes in the lymph nodes of rats corrected with tincture of the safflor plant in chronic carbon monoxide poisoning in an experiment.

The results of a private research.

In chronic carbon monoxide poisoning, positive changes of various nature developed in the morphology of the lymph nodes of experimental rats,

simultaneously corrected with tincture of the safflor plant, a decrease in lymphatic fluid and venous stagnation was observed, and a decrease in the process of lymphostasis. On morphological images, we saw the result of eliminating various types of dilation by reducing stagnation of lymph fluid in all anatomical structures of the lymph node by reducing the expansion of lymph vessels.

Conclusion. A decrease in cells and components reflecting inflammatory processes was found in the sinuses of the lymph nodes. The axillary lymph nodes are macroscopically reduced, the surface is smooth, and the capsule has a normal appearance. Microscopically, the capsule is thinned, and the subcapsular space is sharply reduced. In subcapsular spaces, the components of apoptotic cells, macrophages, histiocytes and reticulocytes are reduced. The cervical lymph nodes are also macroscopically reduced in size compared to the cervical lymph nodes in group 2 rats, their surface is smoothed, the capsule is microscopically thinner than in experimental animals of group 2, and the subcapsular space is normalized.

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